

KINETICS OF HALOGENATION OF FATTY ACIDS PART I. IODINATION OF ACETIC ACID

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The kinetics of iodination of sodium acetate dissolved in glacial acetic acid have been measured at 35° and 25° for sodium acetate concentrations between 0.01 *M* and 1.0 *M* and for iodine concentrations between 0.01*M*—0.05*M*. The reaction rate is found to be nearly bimolecular at the beginning but falls off very rapidly owing to the inhibiting effect of the iodide ions formed during the reaction and also to the opposition caused by the back reaction. The value of k_2 tends to increase with decrease of acetate concentration and lies in the range 1.2 to 1.6 × 10⁻³ mol⁻¹ litre min⁻¹. The energy of activation is of the order of 25,000 calories.

Among lithium, sodium and potassium acetates the speed of reaction is in the order : K > Na > Li, which is also the order of the conductivities of these solutions.

It is surmised that the acetate ion is being iodinated and iodine being an electrophilic reagent, the reaction is favoured by the concentration of negative charge round the α -carbon atom owing to repulsion of electrons from the negative ionic charge at the carboxylate end.

A considerable amount of work has been done on the α -halogenation of saturated aliphatic acids with a view to explaining the mechanism of the reactions involved (Steiner, *Ber.*, 1874, 7, 184; Lapworth, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1904, 85, 41; Aschan, *Ber.*, 1912, 45, 1913; 1913, 46, 2162; Ward, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 1161; 1923, 123, 2207; Watson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 2067; *Chem. Rev.*, 1930, 7, 173; Hell and Urech, *Ber.* 1880, 13, 531; Weston, *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 1373; 1928, 2779). This has, however, been mostly restricted to bromination and chlorination at somewhat elevated temperatures, and usually in presence of catalysts. Very little information, however, is available on the iodination of carboxylic acids. This is, no doubt, due to the relative inactivity of elementary iodine in direct substitution reactions. As a general rule, direct iodination, especially at ordinary temperature, is rather rare and only a very few types of organic compounds are found to undergo direct iodine substitution with any measurable speed at room temperature. Carboxylic acids are, in general, quite stable towards this element even at fairly high temperatures. Watson and Roberts found no reaction to occur when acetic acid was heated with iodine at 100° (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 2779). It has long been known that solutions of iodine in glacial acetic acid can be preserved unchanged for any reasonable length of time and even iodine monochloride, which is a much stronger iodinating agent than iodine itself, has got no appreciable action on glacial acetic acid, which is actually used as a solvent for this reagent (Wij's solution). Bromine and chlorine also do not react with saturated aliphatic acids unless at somewhat elevated temperatures, and many investigators have actually used glacial acetic acid as the medium of reactions involving bromine and iodine (Bartlett and Vincent, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 55, 4993; Nazaki and Ogg, *ibid.*, 1942, 64, 697; Robertson and co-workers, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 179; 1933, 1323; 1937, 337 *et seq.*)

In spite of this inactivity of the carboxylic acids towards halogens, in general and iodine, in particular, it has been observed by one of the authors (Palit) and has already been reported

in course of a previous note (Das, *Science & Culture*, 1948, 14, 165) that a solution of sodium acetate in glacial acetic acid, or propionate in propionic acid and similar systems react with iodine dissolved in the same solvent and that the reaction proceeds with a measurable speed at ordinary temperature. Bromine also reacts in a similar way and more readily than iodine. We have undertaken a detailed study of this reaction with a view to finding out the general characteristics and to elucidating reaction mechanism. The present paper reports the results of a preliminary study of the acetate-acetic acid-iodine system.

It may be mentioned in this connection that iodine has also been found to react with a solution of sodium acetate in glycol, but in this case, it is not known with certainty as to whether the acetate or the glycol is being iodinated, as there is every possibility that glycol itself, though it normally remains practically unaffected by iodine, may react with iodine under the catalytic influence of the acetate. We have therefore chosen acetic acid as the solvent in order to eliminate this uncertainty. We have concerned ourselves mainly with the following physicochemical aspects of the reaction :—

- (i) Light sensitiveness
- (ii) Effect of concentration of the reactants
- (iii) Effect of temperature
- (iv) Effect of other acetates
- (v) Effect of water
- (vi) Effect of added salts
- (vii) Effect of medium.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials.—Sodium acetate was twice recrystallised from water and the crystals were subsequently fused. The fused mass was preserved in a desiccator. Iodine was purified by resublimation over potassium iodide. Glacial acetic acid was partially frozen out and the solid fraction was distilled over 'drierite'. Solutions of iodine in the acetic acid so purified were found to give constant titre values against thiosulphate over a considerable length of time (more than two weeks).

Experiments were carried out at two temperatures, 25° and 35°. The thermostat used for the purpose maintained a constant temperature throughout and maximum variations were within $\pm 0.05^\circ$.

Glass-stoppered bottles were used for the reactions. Five c.c. of reaction mixtures were pipetted out, at definite intervals, into 50 c.c. of water in which potassium iodide was dissolved, in order to arrest the reaction as also to keep the iodine in solution. Titrations were done with *N*/100 standard thiosulphate solution with starch as indicator. Freshly boiled water, well cooled, was used for the purpose. Experimental results were checked and found to be fairly reproducible.

Concentrations of the acetate were varied between the limits 0.01*M*—1.0*M*, but mostly we used rather high concentrations (0.4*M* to 1.0*M*) to maintain the salt effects more or less constant, and also because at such high concentrations of the acetate the reaction was fairly fast and thus convenient for measurements of iodine consumption.

Iodine concentrations were varied between the limits $0.01M$ — $0.05M$, the higher limit being determined by the low solubility of iodine in glacial acetic acid. Further lower concentrations of iodine could not be investigated owing to experimental difficulties. With very low concentrations of iodine, reproducible results could probably be obtained only by the total exclusion of atmospheric oxygen and estimation by colorimetric methods, which we have not done so far.

To economise space we reproduce here only the results obtained with relatively high concentrations of the acetate, the iodine concentrations being restricted to two values. Direct titre values in c.c. of $0.991N/100$ -thiosulphate are given, a typical run in each case being chosen for the purpose. At the foot of each column are given the corresponding values of k_2 (bimolecular constant) calculated from both sets of experiments (which were mostly done in duplicate).

TABLE I

Change of thiosulphate titre with time in presence of diff. conc. of NaAc at 35°.

Conc. of iodine = $0.0241M$.

Time.	1.0M-NaAc.	0.8M-NaAc.	0.6M-NaAc.	0.4M-NaAc.
0 min.	24.30	24.30	24.30	24.30
10	21.85	22.40	22.52	23.10
20	20.70	21.20	21.62	22.46
30	20.05	20.50	21.22	21.96
45	19.30	20.80	20.40	21.36
60	18.80	19.30	19.92	20.96
90	18.10	18.60	19.12	20.15
120	17.75	18.10	18.70	19.65
180	17.10	—	18.04	19.00
24 hours	15.90	16.05	16.35	16.62
$k_2 \times 10^2$ (litres/g. mole min.)	1.28	1.15	1.34	1.56
	1.16	1.15	1.54	1.56

TABLE II

Iodine and sodium acetate at 35°.

Conc. of iodine = $0.01205M$.

	1.0M-NaAc.	0.8M-NaAc.	0.6M-NaAc.	0.4M-NaAc.
0 min.	12.15	12.15	12.15	12.15
10	10.95	11.10	11.20	11.50
20	10.35	10.50	10.72	11.14
30	9.80	10.14	10.42	10.96
45	9.45	9.70	10.02	10.60
60	9.10	9.36	9.76	10.36
90	8.80	9.08	9.30	10.02
120	8.50	8.74	9.04	9.66
180	8.30	8.38	8.62	9.28
24 hours	7.85	8.06	8.08	8.10
$k_2 \times 10^2$ (litres/g. mole min.)	1.17	1.41	1.61	1.66
	1.24		1.61	1.68

TABLE III

Iodine and sodium acetate at 25°

Time	0.8M-NaAc +0.01205M-I ₂	0.4M-NaAc +0.01205M-I ₂
0 min.	12.15	12.15
10	11.82	12.06
20	11.50	11.86
30	11.25	11.72
45	10.92	11.52
60	10.72	11.30
90	10.30	11.10
120	9.98	10.85
180	9.60	10.54
24 hours	8.30	8.18
$k_2 \times 10^3$ (litres/g. mole min.)	0.35 0.33	0.41 0.41

TABLE IV

Effect of other alkali metals.

Temperature = 35°

Time	1.0M-KAc +0.01205M-I ₂	0.4M-LiAc +0.0241M-I ₂
0 min.	12.15	24.30
10	10.12	23.30
20	9.38	22.75
30	8.90	22.50
45	8.60	22.02
60	8.34	21.65
90	8.18	21.04
120	8.04	20.60
180	7.78	19.90
24 hours	7.40	17.0
$k_2 \times 10^3$ (litres/g. mole min.)	2.17 2.24	1.27

As will be seen from above, the reaction rate rapidly falls off with progress of time. This is not only due to the gradual consumption of iodine in course of the reaction, but also, in a greater measure, to the formation of tri-iodide (I₃') with the iodide generated, which results in a decrease of the effective concentration of iodine. Addition of iodides, as expected, strongly retards the reaction. This is naturally a common feature of many reactions involving iodine in which the reaction rate depends on the iodine concentration. For a proper interpretation of the kinetics of the reaction, therefore, a knowledge of the tri-iodide equilibrium in glacial acetic acid is essential. This, however, involves enormous complications in the calculations which could be simplified to some extent by carrying out the reaction in presence of iodide added in excess (cf. Griffith and Mackewon, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1932, 28, 752; Nazaki and Ogg, *loc. cit.*). But at a relatively high concentration of iodide, the reaction becomes inconveniently slow for accurate measurements, and hence it was not possible to carry through in the above manner.

In addition to the tri-iodide formation, there is evidently another complicating factor involved here. The reaction is found to stop, for all practical purposes, in less than 24 hours (or 48 hours with low concentrations of reactants), and even with very high concentrations of acetate, the reaction is never found to reach completion. This has been amply verified by the fact that on keeping the reaction mixture at a constant temperature for two weeks at a stretch, no appreciable change in the titre value was observed after 2 days. All these observations tend to suggest that, in all probability, a state of equilibrium is reached at which the greater portion of the iodine remains unchanged.

Light Sensitiveness.—The reaction has been studied both in diffused daylight and in the dark, and no marked difference has been observed. No photochemical reaction therefore is involved here, at least so far as the visible region of the spectrum is concerned.

Effect of Concentrations of Reactants.—The reaction rate depends on the concentrations of both the reactants. The initial speed is approximately proportional to the first power of

the concentration of each reactant. The absence of exact proportionality is presumably due to the use of concentration terms instead of activity, incomplete dissociation of the acetate in glacial acetic acid which has got a rather low dielectric constant (6.13 at 20°), and also to kinetic salt effects which are naturally quite pronounced at the high acetate concentrations.

The dependence of the reaction rate on the iodine concentration is significant, when compared against the rate of halogenation of ketonic compounds, the latter reaction being zero-order with respect to iodine.

Attempts have been made to fit the experimental results in various kinetic equations, but without any success so far. This is due to the complicating factors discussed above, and hence the initial speed of the reaction has been graphically determined in the following way. The values of $\Delta x/\Delta t$ (where x denotes the iodine consumed at time t) for different values of the mean time were plotted against the mean time (t) whereby a straight line was obtained for the first part of the reaction. On extrapolating the straight line so obtained, $\Delta x/\Delta t$ at $t=0$ was found out from the curve. From the value of $\Delta x/\Delta t$ the velocity constant k was determined from the general equation for a bimolecular reaction :

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = k_2 [\text{Acetate}] [\text{I}_2]$$

For sodium acetate-iodine reaction at 35°, the values of k , so obtained were found to lie in the range $1.2-1.6 \times 10^{-2}$ litre/ g. mole. minute. As will be observed from the tables, this value

Fig. 1 (Upper half)

Fig. 1 (Lower half)

Upper curves : Reactions between 0.4M-sodium acetate and 0.01205M-I₂ at 25° (denoted by circles) and at 35° (denoted by triangles).
 Lower curves : Reactions between 0.8M-sodium acetate and 0.01205M-I₂ at 25° (denoted by circles) and at 35° (denoted by triangles).

has got a tendency to increase with lower acetate concentrations. At 25°, the value of k_2 lies in the range $0.35-0.41 \times 10^{-2}$ (litre/g. mole. minute). The values of k_2 so determined are shown in Tables I-IV, at the foot of the corresponding columns.

Effect of Temperature.—The reaction is much slower at 25° (curve I). Moreover, at the lower temperature, there appears to be a short time lag in the initial period, in which the reaction is very slow. The ratio of $k^{35^\circ}/k^{25^\circ}$ calculated in the above manner was found to be in the neighbourhood of 4, which requires the energy of activation to be of the order of 25,000 g. cal.

Effect of other Acetates.—As evident from Table IV, the speed of the reaction is in the order :K>Na>Li. The value of k_2 for potassium acetate is found much higher (about 80 %) than that for sodium acetate under equivalent conditions, whereas the difference between lithium and sodium acetates is not so considerable. It is significant that this is in the same order as the conductivities of the respective acetates in glacial acetic acid medium (Kolthoff and Wiliman, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 56, 1014).

Effect of Water.—Very small amounts of water added to the reaction mixture are without any appreciable effect, but as the proportion of water is gradually increased, the speed steadily increases and the equilibrium is shifted towards the forward direction. The adjoining curve (Fig. 2) gives the comparative speeds at 25° of the reactions in glacial acetic acid and in 50% acetic acid, from which the pronounced difference will be evident. Reaction in such aqueous solvent is still under a more thorough investigation.

Fig. 2

Reactions between 0.4M-Na acetate and 0.01205M-I₂ at 25° in glacial acetic acid medium (denoted by triangles) and in 50% aqueous acetic acid medium (denoted by circles).

DISCUSSION

It is rather significant that though compounds containing ketonic carbonyl group readily undergo iodination at ordinary temperature, especially under the influence of acids and bases, carboxyl as also carboethoxy compounds are practically inert towards this element. This difference in behaviour of these compounds is easily understood, when viewed in light of the electronic mechanism of organic reactions.

The first step in the halogenation of ketonic compounds is a prototropic change which was first suggested by Lapworth (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1904, 85, 30) and has since been confirmed by

